

EFFECT OF MATRIX ALLOY COMPOSITION ON THE INTERFACIAL PHENOMENA AND MICROSTRUCTURE OF CAST Mg/SiC_P COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the effect of matrix alloy composition on the particle/matrix interfacial phenomena and the SiC particle distribution in the cast Mg/SiC_P composites has been studied. Thermodynamic, heat transfer and kinetic models have been applied to explain the observed particle behaviour (particle pushing/capture) during the solidification of the composites.

INTRODUCTION

The nature of the interface between the matrix and the reinforcement is one of the key factors influencing the mechanical and physical properties of metal matrix composites (MMCs) [1]. Interfacial phenomena and microstructure of cast aluminum MMCs have been extensively studied and relatively well-documented [1-6]. It has been shown [1, 2] that the matrix alloy composition and processing condition can significantly affect the interfacial reactions in aluminum-based composites, and subsequently the microstructure and properties of the materials. However, the research on the same subject for the similar materials using magnesium matrices has received much less attention compared to aluminum based composites.

In recent years, magnesium-based composites, especially those with SiC particulate reinforcement, have been introduced commercially for aerospace and automotive applications because of their low density and superior specific stiffness [7-12]. However, to date no attempt has been made to determine the effect of matrix alloy composition on the Mg/SiC interfacial phenomena and microstructure of the composites. In this paper, SiC particulates have been successfully introduced into pure magnesium and magnesium alloys AZ91 and AS41 matrices via a liquid-mixing and casting process [10] developed at the Institute of Magnesium Technology (ITM). The composites can be produced by conventional permanent mold casting and sand casting processes. This paper describes the particle/matrix interfacial reactions and microstructure of various magnesium alloys reinforced with 10 vol.% SiC particulates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Commercially pure magnesium (designated as PMg), Mg-9wt.%Al-1wt.%Zn alloy AZ91, and Mg-4wt.%Al-1wt.%Si alloy AS41 were selected as the matrices for the composites. The reinforcement particulates are high purity silicon carbide (98.5wt.% β -SiC) with an average diameter of 7 μ m.

Processing of the magnesium matrix composites consisted of mixing pre-heated SiC particulates with magnesium, melt stirring and ingot casting. About 1 kg of composite melts containing 10 vol.% SiC particles were prepared in an electric resistance furnace using a steel crucible under

SF₆/CO₂ atmosphere. The composite melts were held at 700°C for 1 hour, stirred for 2 minutes, and then cast at 700°C into a steel mold to produce ingots of 60 x 80 x 20 mm.

The as-cast MMC ingots were sectioned, polished, and examined under a Leco 300 optical microscope for microstructure. Samples were also analysed via scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using a JEOL 840 SEM coupled with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) system to determine the particle/matrix interfacial reaction products.

RESULTS

PMg/SiC COMPOSITE

Fig. 1(a,b) shows the as-cast microstructure of PMg/SiC composite. The macro-distribution of SiC particles in the pure magnesium matrix is fairly good at the low magnification (Fig. 1(a)). However, at a micro-scale, the SiC particles are more segregated within the intergranular regions, which is more clearly shown in Fig. 1(b). This indicates that during the solidification of PMg/SiC composites, SiC particles were pushed by the growing solid magnesium grains into the intergranular regions.

Magnesium does not form a stable carbide and SiC reinforcement is therefore stable in the pure magnesium melt. This is confirmed by the present work in which no particle/matrix interface reaction products were detected in the PMg/SiC composite. Fig. 2 is a SEM micrograph showing the clear and featureless surface of a SiC particle in the pure magnesium matrix.

Fig. 1. Optical micrographs showing the microstructure of PMg/SiC composite.

Fig. 2. SEM micrograph showing the clean and featureless surface of a SiC particle in PMg matrix.

AZ91/SiC COMPOSITE

The as-cast microstructure of AZ91/SiC composite is shown in Fig. 3(a,b). It can be seen that the composite yields a uniform and homogeneous distribution of reinforcement particles, at both low and high magnifications. It is also evident that in the AZ91 magnesium matrix, a considerable number of SiC particles were captured within the grains (see areas marked "A" in Fig. 3(b)), suggesting a good particle/matrix interfacial wetting during the solidification of the composite.

Although the pure magnesium does not react with SiC, the alloying element such as aluminum in AZ91 matrix alloy can react with SiC to form Al_4C_3 :

In addition, the liberated silicon from this reaction can react further with the molten magnesium to form Mg_2Si :

Fig. 4(a,b) shows that the above reactions have occurred in the AZ91/SiC composite as evidenced by the presence of the reaction product, Mg_2Si , which is normally not a phase that can be found in AZ91 alloy (note the Si content in AZ91 alloy is as low as 50 p.p.m.). The reaction product, Mg_2Si , was detected in the vicinity of the SiC particles as shown in the back-scattered image (Fig. 5(a)), and the EDS analysis (Fig. 5(b)). Fig. 5(a) shows a large number of fine crystals on the SiC particle surface in AZ91/SiC composite. While the crystals were too small for a quantitative EDS analysis, the EDS spectrum (Fig. 5(b)) obtained from the particle surface suggests that the crystals are the complex reaction products containing Si, Mg, Al, C and O.

Fig. 3. (a) Optical and (b) SEM micrographs showing the microstructure of AZ91/SiC composite. (A - intragranular particles)

AS41/SiC COMPOSITE

The as-cast microstructure of AS41/SiC composite as shown in Fig. 6(a) is very similar to that of PMg/SiC (Fig. 1(a)) except for the presence of the matrix precipitates, Mg_2Si , in the former. However, at a higher magnification as shown in Fig. 6(b), it becomes apparent that the reinforcement particles are more evenly dispersed in AS41 than in pure magnesium. On the other hand, Fig. 6(a) also shows that the particle distribution in AS41/SiC is in a more segregated pattern compared with that of AZ91/SiC composite (Fig. 3(a)).

Since AS41 alloy contains 4wt.% Al, a certain extent of particle/matrix interfacial reactions is expected in the AS41/SiC composite, according to Eqs. (1) and (2). However, the presence of

Mg₂Si in the matrix (Fig. 6) cannot be taken as evidence of reactions in this case due to the fact that the matrix alloy itself contains Mg₂Si precipitates, which adds the difficulty to the analysis of reaction products. In addition, the 1wt.% Si content in the liquid magnesium would slow down, or even prevent the reaction (1). In fact, SEM examinations on the SiC particle surface in AS41/SiC specimen show less reaction products, i.e. fewer crystals in Fig. 7, compared to those at the AZ91/SiC interface (Fig. 5(a)).

Fig. 4. (a) SEM and (b) EDS results showing Mg₂Si formation in AZ91/SiC composite.

Fig. 5. (a) SEM and (b) DES results showing complex reaction products (fine crystals) containing Mg, Si, Al, C and O formed at the particle/matrix interface in AZ91/SiC composite.

DISCUSSION

INTERFACIAL REACTIONS - EFFECT OF MATRIX ALLOY COMPOSITION

SiC particles are stable in pure magnesium and no reaction products were found in the PMg/SiC composites. However, in the SiC reinforced Mg-Al alloys such as AZ91 and AS41, particle/matrix interfacial reactions have been evidently shown in this study (Figs. 4, 5 and 7). While no direct evidence of Al₄C₃ formation was given at the AZ91/SiC or AS41/SiC interface, complex reaction products containing Si, Mg, Al, C and O were detected at the both interfaces (Figs. 5 and 7) as fine crystals. Three possible product combinations are postulated for the

complex reaction products: (1) $Mg_2Si + Al_4C_3 + MgO$; (2) $Al_4C_3 + MgO$, assuming that Si is from the SiC particle; and (3) Al-C-O ternary phase, assuming that Mg is from the matrix and Si from SiC. Among the above proposed compounds, MgO was not observed at the interface; and Mg_2Si was usually found adjacent to the SiC particles (Fig. 4), but not at the interface. Recent TEM (transmission electron microscopy) work on a squeeze cast AZ91/SiC composite [12] also failed to show any Al_4C_3 at the particle/matrix interface. Similar results were presented by Laurent et al [13] who studied the interface in a compocast AZ91/SiC composite. The above results seem to suggest that the third speculation, i.e., a Al-C-O ternary phase, is the most likely reaction product found at AZ91/SiC and AS41/SiC interfaces.

Fig. 6. Optical micrograph showing the microstructure of AS41/SiC composite.

Fig. 7. SEM micrograph showing reaction products (fine crystals) at the particle/matrix interface in AS41/SiC composite.

The interfacial reaction can be controlled by (i) surface treatment of reinforcement, (ii) selecting matrix alloy, and (iii) varying the process parameters [9]. While the first approach has been studied by many investigators [2,14,15], and the last one was reported in a previous investigation [10], this study shows the effect of the matrix alloy composition on the interfacial reactions. It is clear from this work that the alloying elements, Al and Si, in the matrix magnesium alloys play an important role in controlling the interfacial reactions. Increasing Al content in magnesium alloys would promote and enhance the particle/matrix interfacial reactions, whereas adding Si to magnesium would restrict and possibly prevent the reactions. This can be easily understood via a thermodynamic analysis of chemical equilibrium for Eq. (1). Similar work on Al/SiC composites has shown that when Si content in aluminum alloys is sufficiently high, reaction (1) can be avoided [1, 16].

MICROSTRUCTURE - SiC PARTICLE DISTRIBUTION

The principal challenge in the solidification processing of metal/ceramic particle composites is to achieve a uniform distribution of the particles in the microstructure of the composites, which depends, to a great extent, on the nature of the particle/solidification front interactions - particle pushing or particle capture. The theory is that when a moving solid/liquid interface (solidification front) approaches a mobile foreign particle suspended in the liquid metal, the particle can be either captured or pushed away by the interface. If foreign particles are captured by the growing solid metal, little redistribution of the reinforcement will occur during solidification, and hence the solidified material will be as uniform as it was in the liquid state. On the other hand, if particles are pushed by the solidification front, they will be redistributed, to be finally segregated in the last pools of liquid matrix to solidify [3]. In this study, both phenomena have been observed in the solidification structures of magnesium matrix composites. Under identical solidification conditions, SiC particles are generally pushed by pure magnesium (Fig. 1(b)) and AS41 (Fig. 7(c)), but some of them are captured by Mg-Al alloy AZ91 (Fig. 4(b)). Considerable efforts have been made to develop criteria for particle pushing/capture [17-22], and a number of theoretical models are established.

(1) *Thermodynamic Model.* Based on a simple thermodynamic criterion and experimental observations, Neumann et al [17, 18] proposed a criterion for particle pushing or capture: particles are pushed if

$$\sigma_{PS} > \sigma_{PL} \quad (4)$$

where σ_{PS} is the particle/solid interfacial energy, and σ_{PL} the particle/liquid interfacial energy.

(2) *Heat Transfer Models.* A thermal conductivity criterion [14] and a heat diffusivity criterion [19] were proposed on the basis of heat transfer analyses in across the particle and solidification front. According to the thermal conductivity criterion, when

$$\frac{k_P}{k_L} < 1 \quad (5)$$

the particles are pushed. The heat diffusivity criterion predicts particle capture if the ratio of heat diffusivities (R) is greater than unity:

$$R = \left(\frac{k_P c_P \rho_P}{k_L c_L \rho_L} \right)^{1/2} > 1 \quad (6)$$

where k_P , c_P and ρ_P represent the thermal conductivity, specific heat and density of the particle, respectively; and k_L , c_L and ρ_L represent the thermal conductivity, specific heat and density of the liquid, respectively.

(3) *Kinetic Model.* From the kinetic point of view, however, under the actual solidification conditions of the metal/ceramic composites, the problem becomes more complicated if the following material- and process-related variables are considered:

- interfacial energies among particle, liquid and solid (σ_{PS} , σ_{PL} and σ_{LS});
- particle radius (r), volume fraction (ϕ), and thermal conductivity (k_P);
- matrix thermal conductivity (k_L) and melt viscosity (η); and
- temperature gradient (G) in front of the solid/liquid interface.

The concept of a critical interface growth rate R_{cr} , below which particles are pushed and above which particles are captured, has been proposed. The influence of the above variables on the critical interface rate of particle capture was summarized by Stefanescu and Dhindaw [20]:

$$R_{cr} = f \left(\frac{\Delta\sigma}{\eta\phi}, \frac{1}{r}, \frac{k_L}{k_P}, G \right) \quad (7)$$

where

$$\Delta\sigma = \sigma_{PS} - (\sigma_{PL} + \sigma_{LS}) \quad (8)$$

The aforementioned criteria were used to predict the particle pushing/capture in the Mg/SiC systems. Table 2 shows the input data and the calculated results for PMg/SiC system based on the thermal conductivity criterion and heat diffusivity criterion (Eqs. (5) and (6)). The both criteria predict particle pushing in PMg/SiC system which is in good agreement with the experimental observation in this paper. While the accurate thermal property data for liquid magnesium alloys AS41 and AZ91 are not available, it is estimated, based on the available data [23, 24], that the properties (k_L , c_L and ρ_L) of liquid magnesium are not very sensitive to alloying elements (aluminum and silicon) in the composition ranges of AS41 and AZ91. It is therefore expected that SiC particles are also pushed by AS41 and AZ91 alloys. This is confirmed in the case of AS41/SiC but not the AZ91/SiC, in which the experimental results clearly show otherwise - particle capture.

Table 1. Input Data and Calculated Results of Heat Transfer Models for Particle Pushing/Capture in PMg/SiC System

Materials	Input Data			Calculated Results	
	k (W/m.K)	c (kJ/kg)	ρ (g/cm ³)	k_p/k_L	R
PMg [21]	80	1.26	1.58	0.19 < 1	0.54 < 1
SiC [22]	15.57	0.963	3.1	(particle pushing)	(particle pushing)

The particle capture effect in AZ91/SiC system may best be explained by the thermodynamic and kinetic models (Eqs. (4) and (7)). While most of the variables in Eq. (7), ϕ , η , r , k_p , G , are identical or slightly different for the systems of AZ91/SiC, AS41/SiC and PMg/SiC, the governing factor which influences the particle capture/pushing is therefore the interfacial energy related terms in Eqs. (4) and (7). Although the interfacial energy data for SiC/Mg(-Al) system are not available, it is believed, based on the heat transfer models and experimental results, that Eq. (4) is obeyed for the system of PMg/SiC, hence, the particles are pushed. Particle pushing was also observed by Inem and Pollard [25] in the SiC particulate reinforced pure magnesium and ZCM630 (Mg-6wt.%Zn-3wt.%Cu-0.5wt.%Mn) alloy, where no particle/matrix interfacial reaction was reported. However, the presence of interfacial reaction products, i.e. the large amount of fine crystals formed at the interface, in the AZ91/SiC system can modify the interfacial structure and increase the interfacial energy σ_{PL} , possibly in excess of the particle/solid interfacial energy σ_{PS} . Eq. (4) is then not satisfied in this case, and some particles are captured by the solidification front in the AZ91/SiC composite. In AS41/SiC system, the reduced interfacial reactions are not sufficient to increase the particle/liquid interfacial energy σ_{PL} in excess of the particle/solid interfacial energy σ_{PS} , particle pushing is then expected in the composite.

CONCLUSIONS

1. SiC particles are stable in pure magnesium and no reaction products were found in the PMg/SiC composites. In the SiC reinforced AZ91, however, particle/matrix interfacial reactions are evidenced by the presence of Mg_2Si phase. Complex reaction products containing Mg, Si, Al, C and O were also observed at the particle/matrix interface in AZ91/SiC and AS41/SiC composites.
2. Increasing Al content in the matrix magnesium alloys would promote and enhance the particle/matrix interfacial reactions, whereas adding Si to magnesium would restrict and possibly prevent the reactions.
3. Under identical solidification conditions, SiC particles are pushed by pure magnesium and magnesium alloy AS41, but captured to some extent by AZ91 alloy as a result of the particle/matrix interfacial reactions.

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